

A THEORY OF MEDICAL CONSUMPTION

EIGHT
ATTENTIONS

LADYBULLENT.COM

**THE
ADVER-
TISEMENTS
DO NOT RECORD ME
AND**

**ADVERTISING
TIS[E]MENTIC
BOMBARD ME
AND CLOUD
MY MIND.**

JEAN-MICHEL BASQUIAT, 1977

YOU CAN CAPTIVATE YOUR AUDIENCE [AND/OR] YOU CAN CATER TO THE QUALITY OF ATTENTION THEY HAVE LEFT TO GIVE.

Every wave of Industrial Revolution and significant innovation comes with its own sensory overwhelm. (See ‘shell shock’ post-WWI or the 1938 ‘War of the Worlds’ radio broadcast or ‘death by GPS.’) However, there’s no time quite like the present when contemplating the assault on human attention, cognition, and memory.

The popular guidance for capturing attention is a moving target. From eight seconds in 2022¹, to six seconds, to three seconds in 2025²—maybe even a single solitary second³—we’re not really paying (quality) attention to all the media we consume.

Never mind the gravity of the world, as relayed to us by our various screens, or the emotional triggers they unleash, or the time we still must commit to actually living in the physical world. There are simply too many competing voices, perspectives, and purchase options that abound.

Here, in the land overflowing with post-cable multichannel streaming, Internet of Things (IoT), digital billboards, contrived virality, and the infinite scroll, the human sensory and cognitive landfill is overflowing.

**AND YET—
WE STILL NEED
THE PEOPLE'S ATTENTION.**

But, over time, strategies that extort attention and **induce hypnosis** rather than offering the courtesy of meaningful value exchange, will inevitably degrade credibility and strain loyalty.

The predictable outcome is burnout: audiences disengage or go numb, and creators are pushed onto a production assembly line that erodes, not only craft, but our most priceless commodity as narrative practitioners, storytellers, and interlocutors of the world: trust.

These cards may help define your creative intent and lighten your audience's mental burden in a more thoughtful, sensory-friendly way.

Model 3

MIND YOUR NERVOUS SYSTEM
 AVOID EYE CONTACT
 CHECK ROUTE
 MIND BELONGINGS
 MANAGE REAX TO ODORS
 BALANCE SPEEDBUMPS
 AVOID BUMPING INTO STRANGER
 SIGNAL INTENT TO STAND
 SAY 'EXCUSE ME'

MAKE OUT WHAT THE CONDUCTOR SAYS OVER THE LOUDSPEAKER
 MAKE ROOM FOR ENTERING PASSENGERS
 CHECK REMAINING BALANCE
 SCAN BILLBOARD ADS
 PLAY MOBILE GAME

cognition perception
 exteroception proprioception
 cognition perception
 cognition perception
 cognition perception
 exteroception
 exteroception cognition perception
 exteroception
 exteroception
 exteroception
 exteroception proprioception exteroception

cognition perception interoception
 proprioception
 MAKE DINNER PLANS
 MAKE LUNCH PLANS
 cognition perception
 exteroception
 exteroception
 cognition perception
 exteroception

PREPARE TO STAND

PLAN SCHOOL PICKUP
 MENTALLY PREPARE FOR FIRST MEETING/CALL

9H 11M
 32 PICKUPS
 34 NOTIFICATIONS
 96 TABS OPEN
 68 UNREAD TEXTS

[EXTEROCEPTION] ⁴
 SIGHT | SOUND | SMELL | TASTE | TOUCH
 [INTEROCEPTION] ⁵
 HUNGER | THIRST
 [PROPRIOCEPTION] ⁶
 BODY AWARENESS
 [NOCICEPTION] ⁷
 PAIN AWARENESS
 [COGNITION+PERCEPTION] ⁸
 SENSEMAKING

LISTEN TO POD
 CHECK E-MAIL

Attention

TRACKING ROUTE
 TRACK ARRIVAL STOP
 COUNTER MOTION
 SICKNESS

HAND-EYE COORDINATION

MIND RESIDUE ON SEAT/RAILS

a snapshot of the sensory landscape your content is in (constant) competition with

Involuntary Attention

WHITE NOISE CONSUMPTION

White noise media consumption is involuntary. We don't have access or authority to 'change the channel.' The proverbial dial, remote, or AUX cord are out of our control.

TVs in airports, bars, gyms • backseat screens in taxis
• music in the grocery store • radio in grandparent's
home

Relaxed Attention

PASSIVE CONSUMPTION

Passive consumption is ambient like “white noise” but deliberate and highly repeatable. It may be intentionally and unintentionally experienced as a secondary or subordinated means of engagement. These media run concurrently with some primary task, or equally distractible task. It may serve a ritualistic or self-soothing purpose.

“comfort” shows watched before bed • “pre-game”
playlists before a night out • morning drive podcast •
YouTube channel played while completing homework

MENU

Distracted Attention

IDLE/NERVOUS CONSUMPTION

Idle consumption may achieve stable engagement, but it is also low-stakes. This kind of media engagement is primarily intended to fill time or alleviate small bouts of boredom or public anxiety. This consumption may not require deep attention, and it may only happen in short bursts, or else it might cause accidents or uncomfortable errors.

PAUSE

scrolling on social media in line for coffee • playing a mobile game while waiting at the DMV • sitting on hold for a call • waiting for a friend at the bar

Full(er) Attention

CONSCIOUS CONSUMPTION

Conscious media consumption is deliberate, intentional engagement. This kind of consumption comes with the expectation that the chosen medium will satisfy one's full attention. This kind of media consumption, likely, involves some level of premeditation.

a bookmarked or queued film • planning to binge a series on a streaming network • a ticketed concert or film

Variable Attention

CURIIOUS CONSUMPTION

Curious consumption is self-directed, but typically prompted by deeper investigation of some primary source of engagement. While that primary source may be another form of media, it doesn't have to be. This is unplanned research sparked by a live question or a simple need to "fact-check" something heard, seen, or even simply considered, imagined, or reflected upon.

fact-checking an article • using a word in conversation, but doubting the meaning • looking up a stock price • mapping transit • wondering what 'goat yoga' is

Passive Attention

CURATED CONSUMPTION

Curated consumption is externally dictated. The sources of media consumption have been selected or suggested by an external authority for a goal that has been explicitly or implicitly agreed or resigned to. This might be coursework, suggested reading lists, or the casual mention of a specific kind of media by an authority figure, respected personality, or institution.

assigned texts in schools • celebrity-recommended
Substack • book club assigned reading • Oprah's Favorite
Things • referral media consumption

NOTE

Any account of media consumption must confront the algorithm, and 'curated consumption' feels the most appropriate place to do so. The role of autoplay and continuous feeds are, arguably, most nakedly apparent in content curation. These mechanics quietly funnel attention into ongoing, artificially curated consumption.

Hacked Attention

COERCIVE CONSUMPTION

Coercive consumption is defined by the viewer/consumer's reactivity. This is media that hijacks the amygdala (the part of the brain that detects threats, and governs emotions like fear and anger). Content that is designed to provoke anger or anxiety is uniquely suited to commandeer attention.

rage-bait • clickbait • discourse spirals • preparing spaghetti on a bare counter • incomprehensible AI content
• 'slop'

Earned Attention

SERENDIPITOUS CONSUMPTION

Serendipitous consumption is characterized by unexpected delight. This can begin as one form of attention and grow into 'serendipity.' It is an unplanned encounter that pleasantly earns more attention than intended or expected.

miss a stop on the subway because the podcast was too good • forget to retrieve food from stove/microwave because too deeply engaged

FOOTNOTES

1

You've Got 8 Seconds to Grab a Customer's Attention. Here's What To Do.

<https://www.entrepreneur.com/growing-a-business/youve-got-8-seconds-to-grab-a-customers-attention-heres/427827>

Reaching Gen Z with video marketing

[https://business.google.com/us/think/search-and-video/video-vision-asos-](https://business.google.com/us/think/search-and-video/video-vision-asos-kantar/#:~:text=second%20cutdowns%20and,-6%2Dsecond%20bumpers,-%2C%20versus%20the%20cutdowns)

[kantar/#:~:text=second%20cutdowns%20and,-6%2Dsecond%20bumpers,-%2C%20versus%20the%20cutdowns](https://business.google.com/us/think/search-and-video/video-vision-asos-kantar/#:~:text=second%20cutdowns%20and,-6%2Dsecond%20bumpers,-%2C%20versus%20the%20cutdowns)

2

8 Tips for Becoming A Successful TikTok Creator

[https://www.tiktok.com/creator-academy/en/article/8-tips-for-becoming-a-successful-TikTok-creator?](https://www.tiktok.com/creator-academy/en/article/8-tips-for-becoming-a-successful-TikTok-creator?lang=en#:~:text=It%E2%80%99s%20important%20to%20hook%20your%20viewers%20within%20the%20first%203%20seconds)

[lang=en#:~:text=It%E2%80%99s%20important%20to%20hook%20your%20viewers%20within%20the%20first%203%20seconds](https://www.tiktok.com/creator-academy/en/article/8-tips-for-becoming-a-successful-TikTok-creator?lang=en#:~:text=It%E2%80%99s%20important%20to%20hook%20your%20viewers%20within%20the%20first%203%20seconds)

3

New Global Research Reveals Dynamics of Consumer Attention in Slower-Scroll, Highly Immersive Environments

<https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20220825005082/en/New-Global-Research-Reveals-Dynamics-of-Consumer-Attention-in-Slower-Scroll-Highly-Immersive-Environments>

4,5

We have more than five senses. A neuroscientist explains the hidden abilities we often overlook (BBC Science Focus Magazine)

<https://www.sciencefocus.com/the-human-body/how-many-senses-do-we-have>

4,5,6

How Many Senses Do We Really Have? (NPR)

<https://www.npr.org/2022/02/01/1077363996/how-many-senses-do-we-really-have>

6,7

Proprioception, Nociception, Exteroception, Interoception — What do they all mean?

<https://www.musicianshealthcollective.com/blog/2016/4/7/proprioception-nociception-exteroception-interoception-what-do-they-all-mean>

8

Cognition and Perception: Is There Really a Distinction?

<https://www.psychologicalscience.org/observer/cognition-and-perception-is-there-really-a-distinction>

8

From Memory and Plasticity to Collective Cognition and AI

<https://www.psychologicalscience.org/publications/observer/memory-plasticity-collective-cognition-ai.html>

Hypnosis is Becoming A Default Engagement Strategy.

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Author ORCID: 0009-0001-1691-0696